

Examining the Views of Teachers on the Difficulties They Experience in Inclusive Education

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Abstract

The research was carried out in order to reveal the difficulties experienced by teachers during inclusive education. Phenomenology, one of the qualitative research designs, was used in the research. 12 teachers working in Sakarya province were determined as the study group. In the research, it was concluded that the teachers received the Internet and the support of experts in the field in preparing IEP, that they had difficulties such as crowded classrooms and student reluctance in IEP implementation, that they had problems with the materials to be used in inclusive education, and that research students had problems in communicating with their families during the inclusive education process. On the other hand, it was concluded that most of the teachers participating in the research did not have any problems with the school administration, and that some teachers avoided cooperating with the teachers about inclusive education. On the other hand, the teachers participating in the research also offered solutions to the difficulties they experienced during inclusive education.

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INTRODUCTION

Human beings need education in order to adapt to the society to which they belong, to improve their existing skills and to acquire new knowledge and skills in social and cognitive areas (Baran, 2021). In this context, the right to education is protected by law. Article 42 of the Constitution of the Republic of Turkey contains regulations on the right to education. According to this article, "No one shall be deprived of the right to education and training. The State takes measures to make those in need of special education useful to society due to their situation". Within the scope of this right granted to people by the Constitution, individuals with special needs who exhibit skills at a different level than their peers in the development process should be supported in order to receive education within the family and at school. (Sönmez & Özcan, 2020). At this point, inclusive education includes the placement of students with disabilities in regular education classes with the provision of all necessary support by educational institutions, so that all people can benefit equally from educational opportunities (Girgin, 2021). Equality of opportunity in education is a right that is included in international conventions to which Turkey is a signatory and accepted by most countries in the world. Students with special needs can benefit from this right through inclusive education practices (Sönmez & Özcan, 2020). In this context, inclusion practices in special education in Turkey started in 1983 with the "Law on Children in Need of Special Education" numbered 2916, and started to be widely implemented in educational institutions with the "Decree Law on Special Education" numbered 573 enacted in 1997 and the "Regulation on Special Education Services" enacted in 2000. (Yazıcıoğlu, 2018). Inclusion can be defined as the continuation of the education of students with special needs in general education classes with their peers with normal development in schools where appropriate educational programs and support services are provided (Sucuoğlu & Kargın, 2010). Support services, on the other hand, can be defined as the provision of tools, equipment, training and consultancy services to people in need of special education, their families, teachers, school and specialized personnel in line with their educational needs determined as a result of medical and educational evaluation and diagnosis (Baran, 2021).

The aim of mainstreaming education can be expressed as ensuring that students with special needs are adapted to the general education environment for as long as possible with the supports they need to achieve success (Girgin, 2021). When mainstreaming education is implemented as planned, the individual differences of each student in the classroom, including mainstreamed students, are revealed and this leads to an educational environment in which all students are valued. In this educational environment, all students are equal. All students see in themselves the right to contribute to classroom activities, lessons and the classroom atmosphere, and in such a classroom environment everyone respects all contributions (Batu, 2008).

Since mainstreamed students are in the same environment with their peers and have different educational needs, teachers have great responsibilities in the educational activities of students with special needs (Girgin, 2021). For a successful inclusive education implementation, it is important that teachers and school staff adopt the inclusive education approach, use effective classroom management and prepare the classroom environment (Kırcaali, 1998). In this context, the role of teachers in the success of the education to be given in the inclusion process, in ensuring social cohesion between the individual with special needs and his peers, and in the involvement of families in the process is very important (Baran, 2021). This situation is also stated in the Special Education Services Regulation as the duties and responsibilities of the teacher working in the mainstreaming class; taking measures for the social acceptance of students by their classmates, making evaluations by taking into account the individual and developmental characteristics of the students, and individualizing and implementing the program of the mainstreaming student (MEB, 2000). Teachers also face some difficulties while performing their duties related to inclusive education. The physical environment that is not suitable for inclusive education, overcrowded classrooms, the school administration leaving the

teacher alone in this process and the resistance of families to accept the student can be expressed as some of the difficulties experienced by teachers (Baran, 2021). For this reason, it is thought that it is important to reveal the difficulties experienced by teachers during the process in order to provide a more beneficial inclusion education. In this context, the research was conducted to determine the opinions of teachers about the difficulties they experience during inclusive education. In the research, the following questions were sought for this purpose;

1. What are the opinions of teachers about the difficulties they experience during inclusive education?
2. What are the opinions of teachers working in inclusive education about the difficulties experienced in cooperation with the school?
3. What are the opinions of teachers working in mainstreaming education about the difficulties they experience in cooperation with the family?
4. What are teachers' suggestions for solutions to the difficulties they experience in mainstreaming education?

METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH MODEL

In this study, a case study, one of the qualitative research methods, was used. The most basic feature of a case study is the in-depth investigation of one or more situations. Factors related to a situation are investigated with a holistic approach and how they affect or are affected by the situation is emphasized (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). In the study, a case study was used to investigate the difficulties experienced by teachers during inclusive education in depth.

WORKING GROUP

In qualitative research, in cases where it is difficult or not possible to conduct applications for the entire universe, it is a solution to include people, events or phenomena that represent the universe in the research (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). In this context, 12 teachers working in Sakarya were selected. While determining the study group, convenience sampling was chosen. Convenience sampling provides speed and practicality to the researcher (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018).

The teachers to be interviewed within the scope of the research were contacted in advance about the date and time of the interview and an appointment was made. Within the scope of the research, interviews were conducted with the teachers on the determined dates and times. The teachers interviewed in the research group were coded as T1, T2, T3..... Information about the teachers interviewed within the scope of the research is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Data on Descriptive Characteristics of Teachers

	<i>Education status</i>	<i>Professional seniority</i>	<i>Related to special education</i> <i>In-service training</i>	<i>Developments related to special education</i> <i>Tracking</i>
T.1	License	16-21 years	No	No
T.2	License	16-21 years	Yes	Yes
T.3	Master's Degree	6-10 years	No	No
T.4	Master's Degree	11-15 years	No	No
T.5	Master's Degree	11-15years	No	No

T.6	License	6-10 years	Yes	No
T.7	License	6-10 years	Yes	No
T.8	License	6-10 y years	No	Yes
T.9	License	21 years and above	No	No
T.10	License	11-15 years	No	No
T.11	Master's Degree	11-15 years	No	No
T.12	License	6-10 years	Yes	Yes

When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that 8 of the teachers participating in the study have bachelor's degree and 4 teachers have master's degree. It is seen that 4 teachers participated in in-service training activities in the field of special education and 8 teachers did not receive in-service training in the field of special education. Again, when Table 1 is examined, it is seen that 3 of the 12 teachers participating in the study follow current developments in special education.

DATA COLLECTION

Semi-structured interview technique was used in the study. In this interview technique, questions are prepared to be used throughout the interview, these questions are asked to the interviewees in the same order, but the interviewee is allowed to answer the questions as he/she wishes during the interview (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). In this context, similar studies in the literature were examined. Semi-structured interview questions were prepared by taking into account the questions in the measurement tools used in the studies. The prepared interview questions were examined by the researchers in the context of the problem statements of the research and the questions that were not deemed appropriate within the scope of the research were removed. The determined questions were organized within the scope of the research problems and a semi-structured interview form was created. The interview form was applied as a pilot study on teachers working in two schools. Within the scope of the pilot study, the questions with low comprehensibility were reorganized, some questions were removed from the interview form and the semi-structured interview form was finalized.

Face-to-face interviews were conducted with the participants on the specified date and time. Teachers were briefly informed about the purpose of the study at the beginning of the interview. A semi-structured interview form was applied to the participants, which included personal information in the first part and questions about the research content in the second part. The interviews lasted 20 minutes.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data obtained in the study were analyzed using content analysis, one of the qualitative research methods. Content analysis aims to define the data and reveal the facts hidden in the data. What is done here is to organize similar data with certain themes in a way that the reader will understand and present them to the reader (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). The data obtained were subjected to content analysis and themes and codes were created based on the themes.

For example, the answers to the first problem of the research, "What do you do about preparing the IEP plan, do you have difficulties?" were brought together to form the themes of "getting to know the student" and "internet".

VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

The fact that the measurement results can be as close to reality and objective as possible ensures that the evaluations to be made according to the results obtained are also appropriate and accurate. For this reason, it is a necessity to utilize measurement tools in the researches to be conducted. In this context, it can be stated as a necessity that the measurement tool to be used in achieving the goal must have qualities such as validity and reliability (Güler, 2019).

Validity can be defined as the ability of the measurement tool used in the research to accurately measure the practice it aims to measure. When accurate measurement is made in a study with high validity, the data collected in the research reflects the reality (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). The following points were taken into consideration in the validity dimension of the study. While creating the interview forms, the relevant literature was reviewed and interview forms were created within the conceptual framework to achieve the purpose of the research. The questions in the form were developed by taking expert opinion. Semi-structured interview questions were applied to some teachers with a pilot application at the beginning of the research. The data obtained as a result of the pilot application were evaluated and as a result of the evaluation, some questions were reorganized and some questions were removed from the measurement tool and the form was finalized.

Reliability refers to reaching the same results with the same participants (Arastaman & Fidan, 2018). The concept of reliability in qualitative research is not so clear. In qualitative research, no two studies are expected to be identical due to the nature of qualitative research. At this point, reliability in qualitative research can be stated as the consistency of the process, not the results (Aydın, 2021). In this context, teachers were given equal time in each interview with the teachers during the implementation. The data collected from the participants during the implementation were subjected to complete evaluation. In this framework, the data obtained from the interviews were analyzed and themes and sub-themes were determined for the answers given to each question. In this context, the fact that the teachers participating in the study voluntarily filled in the consent forms can be expressed as a factor that increases its reliability.

FINDINGS

In this part of the study, the findings obtained as a result of the content analysis of the interviews with the teachers participating in the research are presented.

OPINIONS ABOUT INDIVIDUALIZED EDUCATION PLAN PREPARATION

The views of the teachers participating in the study on the process of preparing Individualized Education Plans are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. *Opinions on the Individualized Education Plan Preparation Phase*

<i>Opinions</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Getting to know the student	9
Internet	4

When Table 2 is examined, it is seen that the answers given by the teachers participating in the research about the process of preparing Individualized Education Plans are gathered under the codes of "getting to know the student" and "internet". The opinions of the teachers participating in the research on this subject are given below:

T. 6. "I measure the student's level of readiness and prepare a plan accordingly, in accordance with the curriculum, at a level that the student can grasp."

T.12. "In this regard, I try to select achievements from the websites of guidance and research centers and download a suitable plan."

DIFFICULTIES EXPERIENCED IN THE INDIVIDUALIZED EDUCATION PLAN IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS

The difficulties experienced by the teachers participating in the study during the implementation of the Individualized Education Plan are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. *Difficulties Experienced in the Individualized Education Plan Implementation Process*

Opinions	Frequency
Class size	5
Student apathy	4
Suitability to student level	3

When Table 3 is examined, it is seen that the difficulties experienced by teachers regarding the Individualized Education Plan implementation process are combined under the codes of "class size, student indifference, and conformity to student level".

The opinions of the teachers about the difficulties they experienced during the Individualized Education Plan implementation process are given below;

T.2. "Crowded classrooms make it difficult to implement Individualized Education Plans. There may be deficiencies in achieving the outcomes."

T.4. "Students are very reluctant."

T.6. "Since we do not know the students well, we sometimes prepare plans above the student level."

DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING ACADEMIC SKILLS

The difficulties experienced by the teachers participating in the study during the teaching process of academic skills are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. *Difficulties Experienced in the Implementation Process of Academic Skills*

Opinions	Frequency
Readiness	5
Repeat/forget	5
Student apathy	3
Class size	2

When Table 4 is examined, it is seen that the difficulties experienced by teachers in the implementation process of academic skills are combined under the codes of "readiness, repetition/forgetting, student apathy, class size".

The opinions of the teachers about the difficulties they experienced during the implementation process of academic skills are given below;

T.9. "The student's illiteracy can be shown among the difficulties we experience."

T.8. "Since the information given to the student about academic skills is not repeated and practiced, we have difficulty in moving to the next stage."

T.10. "Students forget the information they learn in a very short time."

T.4. "Students' attention is either very distracted or reluctant, so they exhibit different situations. Head banging on the desk, making different movements in order to listen to the lesson makes it difficult to convey the desired outcome."

T.2. "It can be difficult to allocate time for students in a crowded classroom environment."

DIFFICULTIES IN ADAPTING TEACHING MATERIALS

The difficulties experienced by the teachers in the process of adapting and using instructional materials are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. *Difficulties Experienced in the Teaching Material Adaptation Process*

<i>Opinions</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Level relevance	5
Class size	2
Source book	2

When Table 5 is examined, it is seen that the difficulties experienced by teachers in the process of adapting and implementing teaching materials are combined under the codes of "suitability to the level, class size, sourcebook".

The opinions of the teachers about the difficulties they experienced in the implementation of teaching materials are given below;

T.4. "The material cannot be fully provided. It is completely left to the teacher to find the material suitable for the level of the child. It is difficult to find resources or visual printed resources suitable for the level."

T.7. "The crowded class sizes make it difficult to apply student-specific teaching materials."

T.8. "While implementing the student plan, I turn to different sources to find examples at a simpler level."

On the other hand, some of the teachers participating in the study stated that they did not use teaching materials. The opinions of the teachers on the subject are given below;

T.1. "We do not use materials at the secondary education level."

T.3. "Unfortunately, we do not use materials."

DIFFICULTIES IN THE EVALUATION PROCESS

The difficulties experienced by the teachers in the process of evaluating students are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. *Difficulties Experienced in the Evaluation Process*

<i>Opinions</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Student reluctance	4
Class size	1

When Table 6 is examined, it is seen that the difficulties experienced by teachers in the evaluation process are combined under the codes "student reluctance, class size".

The opinions of the teachers about the difficulties they experienced during the evaluation process are given below;

T.4. "When evaluating the student, the child is very reluctant to read. He randomly marks the given questions without solving them or resists not doing them."

T.7. "In crowded classroom environments, the level of achievement of the goals set is not measured properly."

On the other hand, some of the teachers participating in the study stated that they did not have any problems in the process of evaluating students. The opinions of the teachers on the subject are given below;

T.2. "There is no problem because I prepare the measurement tool in accordance with the plan prepared during the evaluation."

DIFFICULTIES WITH SOCIAL COHESION AMONG STUDENTS

The opinions of the teachers participating in the research on the difficulties related to social cohesion among students are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. *Difficulties Related to Social Cohesion Among Students*

<i>Opinions</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Peer bullying	8
Reaction	3

When Table 7 is examined, it is seen that the difficulties experienced by teachers in the process of social adaptation between students are combined under the codes "peer bullying, reaction".

The opinions of the teachers about the difficulties experienced in social adaptation between students are given below;

T.6. "Since students are a little more aggressive and challenging during adolescence, they may not attach importance to the sensitivity of our mainstreaming students. Although there are short-term tensions, the problems are solved when teachers intervene."

T.7. "Inclusion students can exhibit behaviors such as swearing against other students."

On the other hand, some of the teachers who participated in the study stated that there were no problems with social cohesion among the students. The opinions of the teachers on the subject are given below;

T.2. "They do not exhibit any negative behavior towards their friends who have IEPs. Their social adaptation is good."

T.8. "Students differ in terms of socialization according to the level of mainstreamed students. In general, their relationships with each other are better."

DIFFICULTIES IN FAMILY COOPERATION

The opinions of the teachers participating in the research on the difficulties experienced in the process of communication with students' families are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Difficulties in Family Cooperation

<i>Opinions</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Contact	8
Non-acceptance	6
Unconscious parent	3
Exclusion	1

When Table 8 is examined, it is seen that the difficulties experienced by teachers in cooperation with families are combined under the codes "communication, non-acceptance, unconscious parents, exclusion".

The opinions of the teachers about the difficulties experienced in family cooperation are given below;

T.1. "Parents mostly communicate with the guidance service. They do not have any meetings with teachers."

T.8. "The parents of mainstreaming students have difficulties in accepting the student's situation."

T.5. "Parents are unconscious."

T.7. "Some parents take care of their normal children and do not support their mainstreamed child sufficiently."

DIFFICULTIES WITH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT

The opinions of the teachers participating in the research on the difficulties they experience with school administration are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Difficulties experienced with school management

<i>Opinions</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Cooperation	4
Venue	2

When Table 9 is examined, it is seen that the difficulties experienced by teachers with school administration are combined under the codes of "cooperation, space".

The opinions of the teachers about the difficulties experienced with the school administration are given below;

T.4. "School administration is mostly involved in the procedural part of the work. In the process of communication with the family, the school administration stays out of the process."

T.6. "We do not have a fixed room where we can do support education because the school building is inadequate."

The majority of the teachers participating in the study (8) stated that they did not have any problems with the school administration. The opinions of the teachers on the subject are given below;

T.2. "I did not have any administrative problems."

SOLUTION SUGGESTIONS FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

The solution suggestions of the teachers participating in the study regarding the problems experienced in inclusive education are shown in Table 10.

Table 10. *Suggestions for solutions to the difficulties experienced in inclusive education*

<i>Opinions</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Trainings	6
Venue	6
Cooperation	5
Material	4
Target/gain	3
Specialists	3

When Table 10 is examined, it is seen that the solution suggestions of the teachers about the problems experienced in inclusive education are combined under the codes of "trainings, space, cooperation, material, target/gain, and experts".

The opinions of the teachers about their suggestions for solutions to the problems experienced in mainstreaming education are given below;

T.8. "Students and parents should be informed about inclusive education, and the importance of school family student cooperation should be emphasized with seminars."

T.1. "There should definitely be a special environment for special students. Considering the situation of each student, all necessary materials should be available in this special place."

T.10. "Guidance service should cooperate more with teachers in inclusive education and in preparing Individualized Education Plans."

T.12. "Classrooms with rich materials for special education should be established in schools."

T.2. "Outcome lists can be created for the Individualized Education Plan."

T.4. "A separate educator and experts in this field should be assigned to each school for mainstreaming students."

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The aim of the study was to reveal the difficulties experienced by teachers during inclusive education. In this context, 12 teachers were interviewed and as a result of the interviews, teachers' responses were received on the following themes: Individualized Education Plan preparation process, difficulties encountered in the Individualized Education Plan implementation process, materials used in Individualized Education Plan implementation, measurement and evaluation in Individualized Education Plan implementation, socialization between mainstreamed students and other students, difficulties experienced with the families of mainstreamed students, difficulties encountered with the school administration and teachers' suggestions for solutions to the problems experienced in the inclusive education process.

The teachers who participated in the research were found to first determine the readiness level of the student and to determine the level of the student in the process of preparing the Individualized Education Plan. On the other hand, it was concluded that some of the teachers participating in the study actively used the internet in the process of preparing the Individualized Education Plan and especially benefited from the information prepared by experts on the websites of guidance and research centers. Baran (2021), Yorulmaz (2015) and Sadioğlu (2011) concluded in their studies that teachers received help from experts while preparing the Individualized Education Plan.

The majority of the teachers participating in the study stated that they encountered difficulties in the implementation of the inclusion program due to the crowded class sizes during the Individualized Education Plan implementation process during inclusive education. In this context, it can be stated that the crowded class sizes make the Individualized Education Plan implementation process difficult in mainstreaming education. On the other hand, teachers stated that mainstreaming students were not interested in the process of Individualized Education Plan implementation. It can be stated that this situation disrupts the process of maintaining the implementation in a healthy way. Baran (2021), Karaca (2018), Özgüneş (2016), Gök (2013), Saraç and Çolak (2012), Sadioğlu (2011), Orhan (2010), Batu and Topsakal (2003) concluded in their studies that the crowded class sizes make the process of Individualized Education Plan implementation difficult. With this result, the research is similar to other studies in the literature.

Regarding the difficulties experienced in teaching academic skills, the teachers who participated in the research stated that the low level of student readiness negatively affects the learning of academic skills. On the other hand, it was concluded that the fact that the student does not repeat the information learned at school in the home environment causes the student to forget all the information learned. On the other hand, the teachers who participated in the study stated that the student's lack of interest in the process and the overcrowded classrooms caused difficulties in learning the academic skills of mainstreaming students. Düşünür (2018) concluded in his research that students' academic development is slow.

The teachers who participated in the research stated that they had problems with the materials to be used during inclusive education. In this context, teachers stated that the existing materials were not at the level of mainstreaming students and that materials suitable for the level of mainstreaming students could not be found. From the teachers' thoughts on this issue, it can be concluded that there are problems in finding and using materials in inclusive education. Baran (2021), Balo (2015), Sadioğlu (2011), Kargın (2003), Bilen (2007) also concluded in their studies that there are problems in providing materials to be used during inclusive education.

Regarding the difficulties experienced in the evaluation process, the teachers who participated in the research stated that inclusion students were reluctant in the evaluation process. In this context, it was concluded that students were reluctant in actions such as reading, answering and writing questions during the evaluation, which made measurement and evaluation difficult. Saraç and Çolak (2012) concluded in their study that teachers had difficulties in the process of assessing mainstreaming students. On the other hand, some of the teachers participating in the study stated that they did not have any problems in measurement and evaluation. Baran (2021) also concluded that teachers did not experience any difficulties during assessment.

The teachers who participated in the study stated that there are sometimes problems between mainstreaming students and non-inclusion students. In this context, it was concluded that inclusion students had difficulty in accepting their friends, excluded their friends, and sometimes exhibited mocking behaviors about their friends' situations, and in this context, inclusion students were subjected to peer bullying. On the other hand, teachers stated that mainstreaming students also exhibit aggressive situations from time to time and unintentionally disturb their other friends. Baran

(2021), Gök (2013), Sadioğlu (2011) and Ataman (1996) also concluded that there are problems in social adaptation between mainstreaming students and other students in the classroom. In this context, the research is similar to the studies in the literature. In his study, Düşünür (2018) concluded that non-inclusive students did not have problems with inclusive students in the classroom, on the contrary, their positive feelings such as sharing and helping were reinforced.

During the inclusion education process, teachers evaluated the problems they experienced with the families of mainstreaming students under the title of communication and acceptance. The teachers who participated in the research stated that they had difficulty in communicating with the families of mainstreaming students and that this situation negatively affected inclusion education. On the other hand, it was stated by the teachers participating in the study that the families did not accept the special conditions of the students and therefore the process was negatively affected. On the other hand, the teachers who participated in the study also concluded that the families of mainstreaming students are unconscious about mainstreaming education. Baran (2021), Düşünür (2018), Yılmaz (2015), Balo (2015), Güzel (2014) and Sadioğlu (2011) concluded in their studies that mainstreaming students have problems with their families.

Most of the teachers participating in the study stated that they did not have any problems with the school administration during the research training. On the other hand, a few teachers stated that the school administration did not attach importance to inclusive education and avoided cooperation because they considered the issue only as paperwork. Baran (2021) also concluded that the school administration did not cooperate during the process. The research is similar to the research in the literature.

The teachers who participated in the study expressed solutions to the difficulties experienced during inclusive education, such as giving seminars to teachers, parents and students about inclusive education, creating special areas in schools where inclusive education will be carried out, assigning experts to manage the process other than school teachers related to inclusive education, and preparing materials to be used during inclusive education and delivering them to teachers who carry out the process. Saraç and Çolak (2012) concluded in their study that the participants stated that seminars should be given to teachers, school administrators and families about inclusive education. Deniz and Çoban (2019) concluded that teachers should have special areas for inclusive education in schools.

SUGGESTIONS

- 1- It is recommended to prepare visual materials about inclusive education that teachers can use during the process.
- 2- Seminars can be organized for teachers, parents and students on inclusive education.
- 3-A special place can be created in each school to carry out inclusive education in a healthier way.
- 4-Out-of-school activities can be organized to ensure school, student and parent cooperation.
- 5-Participation in out-of-school cultural, social and artistic activities can be encouraged for the socialization of students.
- 6-Work can be done with the families of mainstreamed students on inclusion education.
- 7-Study can be conducted to determine the school administration's perspective on mainstreaming education.

8-Study can be conducted to determine the attitudes of other students in the class other than mainstreaming students towards their friends receiving mainstreaming education.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

- The first author made significant contributions to the conception, design, acquisition of data, analysis and interpretation of data.

- The second author was involved in drafting the article, critically revising it for important intellectual content, and finalizing the version for publication.

REFERENCES

- Arastaman, G. and Fidan, İ. (2018). Validity and reliability in qualitative research: A theoretical review. *YYÜ Journal of Faculty of Education*, 15(1), 37-75. Retrieved from: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/yyuefd/issue/40566/491262>
- Ataman, A. (1996). Training faculty members for education faculties that train teachers and total quality management in education. *Yeni Türkiye (Education Special Issue)*, 2 (7), 382- 389. Access address: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/ufuksbedergi/issue/57448/814825>
- Aydın, S. (2021). Validity and reliability in qualitative research. M. Çelebi (Ed.). *Qualitative Research Methods*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi
- Balo, E. (2015). İlkokullardaki kaynaştırma eğitimi uygulamalarında karşılaşılan sorunlar ve çözüm önerileri. (Yayın No. 383514), [Yüksek lisans tezi, Fırat Üniversitesi]. Yükseköğretim Kurulu Tez Merkezi, Türkiye.
- Baran, E. (2021). Investigation of the opinions of classroom and guidance teachers about the difficulties they experience in mainstreaming education, (Publication No. 681560) [Master's thesis, Biruni University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center, Turkey.
- Batu, E. S. (2008). What teachers can do in their classrooms for a successful inclusion practice. *İlköğretmen Eğitimci Dergisi*, 18, 26-28. Retrieved from: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/adyuebd/issue/24588/260309>
- Batu, S. and Topsakal, M. (2003). Special education counseling process and a counseling example. *Journal of Special Education*, 4(1), 19-29. Access address: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/ozelegitimdergisi/issue/17199/179625>
- Bilen, E. (2007). Classroom teachers' opinions on the problems they encounter in mainstreaming applications and solution suggestions, (Publication No. 211466) [Master's thesis, Dokuz Eylül University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center Turkey.
- Deniz, E. & Çoban, A. (2019). Teacher views on inclusive education. *Electronic Journal of Social Sciences*, 18(70), 734-761. Retrieved from: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/esosder/issue/43078/448379>
- Düşünür, A. (2018). Teachers' opinions on the problems encountered in inclusive education in primary schools. (Publication No. 506813) [Master's thesis, Pamukkale University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center, Turkey.
- Girgin, İ. (2021). Educators' professional development needs for inclusion. *International Journal of Community Research*, 18, 4151-4175. Retrieved from: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/opus/issue/63558/845376>
- Güler, N. (2019). *Measurement and Evaluation in Education*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi
- Güzel, N. (2014). Problems experienced by primary school teachers with mainstreaming students regarding mainstreaming education (Beykoz district example), (Publication No. 355918) [Master's thesis, Yeditepe University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center, Turkey.

- Karaca, M. A. (2018). The effect of inclusion education program on teachers' professional competencies in inclusion practices, (Publication No. 509031) [Master's thesis, Necmettin Erbakan University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center, Turkey.
- Kargın, T. (2004). Inclusion: definition, development and principles. Ankara University Faculty of Educational Sciences Journal of Special Education, 5(2), 1-13. Retrieved from: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/ozelegitimdergisi/issue/17196/179604>
- Kırcaali, İ. G., (1998). Inclusion and Support Special Education Services. Journal of Special Education, 17-22. Access address: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/315606147>
- MONE. (2000). Special Education Services Regulation. Ankara: National Education Press House.
- Orhan, M. (2010). Examination of the level of social skills and problem behaviors of pre-school mainstreaming students and students with normal development and teachers' opinions on mainstreaming (Publication No. 265725) [Master's thesis, Anadolu University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center, Turkey.
- Öz, A. (2016). The views of classroom teachers who have mainstreaming students in their classrooms in the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus on the problems experienced in mainstreaming education. (Publication no: 402786), [Master's thesis, Girne American University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center, Turkey.
- Sadioğlu, Ö. (2011). A qualitative research on the problems, expectations and suggestions of classroom teachers regarding inclusion. (Publication No. 306363) [Master's thesis, Uludağ University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center, Turkey.
- Saraç, T., & Çolak, A. (2012). Opinions and suggestions about the problems encountered by primary school classroom teachers in the process of mainstreaming practices. Mersin University Journal of Faculty of Education, 8(1), 13-28. Retrieved from: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/mersinefd/issue/17379/181509>
- Sönmez, N. & Özcan, B. (2020). A descriptive analysis of postgraduate theses on inclusive education in primary school in Turkey. Journal of Yaşadıkça Education, 34(1), 1-27. Retrieved from: <http://journals.iku.edu.tr/yed/index.php/yed/article/view/121>
- Sucuoğlu, B. and Kargın, T. (2010). Inclusion practices in primary education. Ankara: Kök Publishing.
- Yazıcıoğlu, T. (2019). Guidance teachers' views on the functioning of the individualized education program (bp) unit. Anemon Muş Alparslan University Journal of Social Sciences, 7(5), 225-234. Access address: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/825476>
- Yılmaz, E. (2015). Bir ilkokuldaki öğretmenlerin kaynaştırma uygulamaları hakkında görüşleri (Publication No. 407803) [Master's thesis, Anadolu University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center, Turkey.
- Yorulmaz (2015). Problems encountered by primary and secondary school teachers in inclusive education in Batman province example, (Publication No. 440013) [Master's thesis, Zirve University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center, Turkey.
- Yıldırım, A. & Şimşek, H. (2018). Qualitative research methods in social sciences (11th edition). Ankara: Seçkin Publications.